

Challenges in communicating uncertainty of food life cycle assessment (LCA) results

Tuomas J. Mattila, Finnish Environment Institute SYKE

(Not yet peer reviewed preprint. Submitted for peer review in March 2021.)

A recent article by Pieper et al.¹ estimated the external costs of foodstuffs using results from life cycle assessment (LCA). In the study, the certainty of the conclusions compared to the uncertainty of the data sources highlighted a problem in using LCA for decision support: numbers are transmitted, but the uncertainty and assumptions are not.

Detailed guidance (ILCD) has been developed to help in using LCA to compare products fairly (same system boundary and scope) and to interpret results (uncertainty analysis)². Interpretation of Food LCA has two additional challenges: uncertainty in nitrous oxide N₂O emissions and soil carbon (C) sequestration. The LCA community knows these issues, but this inherent knowledge of uncertainty does not get transmitted to the users of the data in other disciplines. Aggregating the emissions to a combined CO₂-equivalent makes it difficult to evaluate the extent of this uncertainty from published articles or to update the results when methods improve.

Soil nitrous oxide emissions often dominate LCA climate impact category for agricultural products. They are estimated with IPCC emission factors³, which convert N applied to N₂O emitted. These emission factors are provided for different situations (pasture, manure, fertilizer, indirect, etc.) and are very uncertain, with an uncertainty factor of three (i.e. 1% emission can range between 0.3-3%)³. The emissions of conventional and organic farming have different mechanisms, and N₂O emissions from legumes can be much lower than from fertilizer sources⁴. As additional research has been published, IPCC has updated the emission factors. In the 2019⁵ refinement, the emission factor from manure in pastures (largest agricultural N₂O source globally⁶) was decreased from 0.7-6% to 0-1.4% (factor 5 reduction). Neither the high uncertainty nor the sensitivity of the results to emission factors was transferred from the LCA studies in the meta-analysis to the conclusions in Pieper et al.

In addition to uncertainty in included emissions, there is the uncertainty in omitted carbon sequestration. Although soil C sequestration is increasingly identified as a key negative emission technology⁷, it continues to be commonly ignored ("cut-off") in LCA due to data limitations and methodological issues^{8,9}. Methods for including soil C have been presented since at least 2007¹⁰ and where soil C has been included, it has dominated the results, sometimes resulting in net negative climate impacts^{8,11}. Currently soil C is often omitted due to value choices⁹, but the reasons and importance of this omission are not communicated to those using the LCA results.

Because the inherent uncertainties in food LCA, the only robust conclusions are either conditional or probabilistic. One approach to managing uncertainty would be a Monte Carlo simulation followed by a global sensitivity analysis¹² of the differences between food categories. This can be illustrated with a simple example: comparing rapeseed oil to pastured beef (based on energy content, just for illustration). The beef calculation used climate impact from ¹¹, but updated N₂O emissions to 2019 emission factors⁵ and used the range of soil C sequestration from ^{7,11}. The rapeseed oil calculation used climate impact from ¹, separated that to components and added the soil C using ⁸. In addition, cover crops were added 50% of the rapeseed simulation runs using¹². The uncertainties were characterized as lognormal distributions and propagated using Monte Carlo with 10000 simulations. The results of this example Monte Carlo are presented in Fig 1: Although the beef had a much higher median climate impact than rapeseed oil, in 27% of simulation runs beef had smaller impacts. Assumptions on soil C explained 99% of variation in the difference. If soil C sequestration would be higher than 2.1 t C/ha/yr, beef would have lower emission intensities. Therefore the comparison depends completely on amount of carbon sequestration¹¹ and the agreed upon calculation methodology⁹. While these remain uncertain, no broad conclusions can be made on the comparison and studies using point estimates can reach completely opposite conclusions.

Including uncertainty may make broad conclusions impossible, but also reveals positive outliers and key performance indicators. As LCA practitioners, we should take more care to communicate also the uncertainties and assumptions behind the results and format the data in a manner, which makes updating and recalculating after method changes possible. Meanwhile, users of food LCA results should ask at least two questions to estimate the magnitude of the uncertainty: how were N₂O emissions estimated and was soil C included?

Figure 1. The difference between the climate impact of beef and rapeseed oil depends strongly on the assumptions made on soil carbon sequestration (Note: only N₂O and soil C from grazing and cover crops have been included as sources of parameter uncertainty for this illustration.)

1. Pieper, M., Michalke, A. & Gaugler, T. Calculation of external climate costs for food highlights inadequate pricing of animal products. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, (2020).
2. ILCD. *General guide for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) - Detailed guidance*. (Joint Research Centre, Institute for Environment and Sustainability, 2010).
3. IPCC. *2006 IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories*. (2006).
4. Jensen, E. S. *et al.* Legumes for mitigation of climate change and the provision of feedstock for biofuels and biorefineries. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* **32**, 329–364 (2012).
5. IPCC. *Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*. (IPCC, 2019).
6. FAOSTAT. FAOSTAT Database. <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home> (2020).
7. Paustian, K., Larson, E., Kent, J., Marx, E. & Swan, A. Soil C Sequestration as a Biological Negative Emission Strategy. *Front. Clim.* **1**, (2019).
8. Brandão, M., Milà i Canals, L. & Clift, R. Soil organic carbon changes in the cultivation of energy crops: implications for GHG balances and soil quality for use in LCA. *Biomass Bioenergy* **35**, 2323–2336 (2011).
9. Brandão, M. *et al.* Key issues and options in accounting for carbon sequestration and temporary storage in life cycle assessment and carbon footprinting. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* **18**, 230–240 (2013).
10. Milà i Canals, L. *et al.* Key elements in a framework for land use impact assessment in LCA. *Int. J. LCA* **12**, 5–15 (2007).
11. Stanley, P. L., Rowntree, J. E., Beede, D. K., DeLonge, M. S. & Hamm, M. W. Impacts of soil carbon sequestration on life cycle greenhouse gas emissions in Midwestern USA beef finishing systems. *Agric. Syst.* **162**, 249–258 (2018).
12. Saltelli, A. *et al.* *Global sensitivity analysis: the primer*. (Wiley-Interscience, 2008).
13. Poeplau, C. & Don, A. Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils via cultivation of cover crops – A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* **200**, 33–41 (2015).